

INVESTIGATIONS INTO THE REACTIVITY OF CARBON TETRABROMIDE,
PART I. BEHAVIOUR OF CARBON TETRABROMIDE WITH PHENOLS IN THE
PRESENCE OF ALKALI AND ANHYDROUS ZINC CHLORIDE

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Carbon tetrabromide, unlike the tetrachloride, forms with phenol in aqueous alkaline solution substantial amount of aurin. In the other reactions also it shows greater reactivity.

Reactions of carbon tetrachloride with phenols are well known. One is illustrated by the classical method of Reimer and Tiemann (*Ber.*, 1876, 9, 1285; 1877, 10, 2185) of preparing phenolic acids. Zeltner and Landau (D.R.P., 25887) introduced the use of copper in this reaction and as its result claimed to obtain excellent yields of the phenolic acids, 55% with phenol, 85% with *o*-cresol and within these limits in other cases. Their procedure was to boil for 8 hours the tetrachloride and the phenol in molecular proportions together with 6 molecules of caustic potash in 40% solution and 0.3 parts of copper. Later, Bains and Driver (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 1214) passed vapours of the tetrachloride over heated potassium phenate at 175° in the hope of finding the intermediates in the Reimer and Tiemann's synthesis, but instead they obtained aurin in 75% yield. There was no reaction at lower temperatures and no improvement in the yield of aurin with excess of alkali. With *o*-cresol the product was 3:3':3"-trimethylaurin.

Regulating the conditions of temperature and the amount of anhydrous zinc chloride, Gomberg and Snow working with carbon tetrachloride and phenol (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 198) obtained principally diphenyl carbonate, *pp*"- and *op*'- dihydroxybenzophenone and aurin. In the preparation of aurin, however, *p*-hydroxyphenylfluorone, the *op*'*p*" analogue of aurin, *leuco*-aurin, *p*-hydroxyphenylxanthane also resulted. The latter, except *leuco*-aurin, had in their molecules the tetrabromide carbon atom fixed in *op*'- or *oo*'- position with respect to the phenol nucleus and constituted in all about one fourth the amount of aurin.

In the light of the above investigations, it was felt of interest to ascertain how carbon tetrabromide would react with phenol in aqueous alkaline solutions, with potassium phenate and with phenol in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride. The results of such a study are recorded in the present investigation.

When carbon tetrabromide, phenol and caustic potash (1 : 1 : 6) are boiled in aqueous solution in the presence of copper, as in the case of the tetrachloride (Zeltner and Landau, *loc. cit.*), the reaction to give *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid and salicylic acid goes to a smaller extent (31%) compared to the formation of a dye shown to be aurin (46%). In the mixture of the phenolic acids, the *p*-isomer is the main constituent (80%). The reaction mixture contains the dye even from an early stage of heating. The yield of the acids can be made to rise (68%) if the heating at first be gentle, though some aurin (25%) is still obtained. Results are more or less similar in the absence of copper. Also, *o*-cresol, even under gentle heating, gives phenolic acids only to a small extent (29%), composed almost entirely of the *p*-isomer, 4-hydroxy-*m*-toluic acid, the product again being a dye of the aurin type (62%). With *p*-substituted phenols, the yield of the acids is still lower and the reaction mixture contains neutral matter.

Dry heating of carbon tetrabromide with potassium phenate gives aurin under conditions milder (110°) than those employed (175°) in the case of the tetrachloride. In the experiments

where the tetrabromide is treated with phenol and zinc chloride substantial amount of aurin is obtained under mild conditions. In the preparation of aurin with CBr_4 , the byproducts (*op'* and *oo'* derivatives, *vide supra*) reach almost equal in proportion with aurin.

As one experiment shows, CCl_4 itself does not give with phenol even a trace of aurin in aqueous alkaline solution. The behaviour of the tetrabromide under such conditions may then be summed up, taking note also of a simultaneous hydrolytic decomposition, as follows:—

For the reaction (i) to occur favourably, it is desirable to keep the temperature below 100° in the early stages. Ordinarily the reaction (ii) will be favoured as compared to (i) and (iii).

From the above results carbon tetrabromide appears to be more reactive and further, can attack the phenol nucleus with greater avidity than is the case with the tetrachloride.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preliminary experiments showed that carbon tetrabromide (3.32 g., 0.01M) when boiled for 5 to 6 hours with 40% caustic potash (0.06 M, 3.36 g. in 8.6 g. H_2O) in the presence of copper-bronze (0.05 g.) suffered a decomposition of 32.5%. In the absence of copper it was 11.5%.

Boiling of Carbon Tetrabromide with Phenol in the presence of Copper-bronze and Aqueous KOH (6 mol. proportion).—A mixture carbon tetrabromide (8.52 g., ca. 0.025M), phenol (2.35g., 0.025 M), and a 40% solution of caustic potash (9.85 g. in 14.7 c.c. H_2O ; ca. 0.15M), copper-bronze (0.075 g.) and alcohol (2-3c.c.) to dissolve the carbon tetrabromide tending to deposit itself inside the condenser tubing was refluxed for 8 hours. The liquor in the flask developed a deep magenta colour within 10 minutes of heating. After 8 hours, the reaction mixture was just neutralised with 2N acetic acid and then steam distilled to remove unreacted phenol and carbon tetrabromide. The solid left behind in the mixture was extracted with alkali. The filtered magenta coloured extract upon neutralisation with acetic acid yielded a brown-red precipitate (A; 1g.) and a filtrate (B).

The powder (A) was dried at 120° when it showed a metallic lustre. The dried sample dissolved in alkali with a deep magenta colour, and in alcohol and glacial acetic acid with a yellowish red colour. After reduction with zinc dust and acetic acid, aq. alkali failed to produce any colour. It was restored by addition of fresh alkaline potassium ferricyanide (cf. Dale and Schorlemmer, *Annalen*, 1873, 166, 286). Moreover, the dried powder was almost (90%) ether-insoluble, m.p. 260° (decomp.). It could be extracted almost entirely with 1.5% ammonium hydroxide solution from which with acetic acid was obtained by re-precipitation a more pure sample, m.p. 300° (decomp.). These properties agree with those of aurin. This was confirmed by the conversion of the dried product (A) into the triacetyl derivative of aurin, m.p. 170° , by the method of Gomberg and Snow (*loc. cit.*).

The filtrate (B) was saturated with sulphur dioxide, and the residual liquor extracted with ether. The ether extract yielded a mixture of phenolic acids (1.04g., 33%). In it, 80% mass was chloroform-insoluble and comprised *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p., 204°; ethyl ester (vide Hewitt and Winnill, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 446), m.p. 112°. The chloroform-soluble fraction contained salicylic acid, giving violet colour with ferric chloride.

When this experiment was repeated with carbon tetrachloride no trace of aurin could be isolated. Phenolic acids (1.5 g.), however, were formed as was to be expected.

With the tetrabromide, again, in the absence of copper 66% aurin and allied products and 21% phenolic acids had resulted. Aurin was formed in poor yield if the tetrabromide, phenol and caustic potash were taken in the ratio 1 : 1 : 3 or 1 : 3 : 3, using copper. Also, when the proportions were kept 1 : 1 : 6 as usual, but heated at 70° for 3 hours and at 100° for 5 hours, formation of aurin went down to 34% and of acids rose to 67%.

Boiling of Carbon Tetrabromide with o-Cresol in presence of Copper and of KOH (6 mol. proportion).—The experiment was carried out with *o*-cresol (2.7g., 0.025 *M*) as in the case of phenol, but the heating was done at 70° for 3 hours and at 100° for 5 hours. A dye of the aurin type (1.7g., 62%), probably 3 : 3 : 3'-aurin and phenolic acids (1g., 29%) resulted. In the latter, the CHCl₃-insoluble fraction was 4-hydroxy-*m*-toluic acid (0.95g., 27%), m.p. (purified) 170-72°; ethyl ester, m.p. 98° (vide Auwers, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 3174). The CHCl₃-soluble portion gave violet colour with ferric chloride solution, presumably due to the 6-hydroxy-*m*-toluic acid (0.05g., 2%). Reaction with *p*-cresol, *p*-bromophenol gave very poor yield of phenolic acids (10-14%), the bulk of the matter obtained was of a neutral character.

Reaction of Carbon Tetrabromide with Potassium Phenate.—The tetrabromide (3.32 g., 0.01 *M*) was heated with potassium phenate (3.96 g., 0.03 *M*) in the presence of copper-bronze (0.075 g.) in a loosely corked boiling tube first at 110° when the reaction started with a great violence giving a deep fuchsine colour to the reaction mixture. Afterwards it was heated at 120°-140° for 6 hours. The isolation of the dye was effected with the faintly alkaline residue by precipitation with 2*N* acetic acid and removing excess of CBr₄ and phenol by steam distillation, yield 1.48 g. (52%). Also under the above conditions of experiment if more caustic potash (1.70 g.) was added, the yield of aurin remained much the same. The change was somewhat less in the absence of copper.

Reactions of Carbon Tetrabromide with Phenol in the presence of Anhydrous Zinc Chloride.—Phenol (33 g., 0.35 *M*), fused and powdered zinc chloride (5 g.) and carbon tetrabromide (33.2 g., 0.1 *M*), all intimately mixed, were heated at 135° till the vapours of HBr ceased to come (ca. 20 hrs.) The red-brown viscous product was steam distilled to remove excess of phenol, the whole mass was then poured into water (200 c.c.) containing hydrochloric acid (6 c.c.). The mixture was filtered and the residue washed with water. It was repeatedly digested at 70°-80° with 1.5% ammonia. The ammonia-insoluble matter left behind represented the *opp*-carbinol or its fuchsine and allied products (amount 6.8g.) The combined ammonia extracts were acidified with dilute acetic acid (1 : 4). The weight of the crude dye precipitated was 9g.

The crude dye was kept over ether (50 c.c.) overnight. The ether extract gave a residue, representing the mixture of *pp*'- and *op*'- dihydroxybenzophenones (2g., 6%).

The ether-insoluble product was aurin, m.p. 290-300° (decomp.) (7.1g., 21%). Triacetate, m.p. 172-73°.

In a separate experiment, when less catalyst and milder heating were employed (cf. Gomberg and Snow, *loc. cit.*, p. 201) no diphenyl carbonate was found to be present. Instead, mixtures of ketones (23-56%) and aurin only resulted.